

FINE ART TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This article talks about the technologies of fine arts and their development in the period of independence, the created conditions.*

Key words: *visual art technologies, "Art-graphics", "Art studies", copying.*

ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ИЗОБРАЗИТЕЛЬНОГО ИСКУССТВА

Аннотация. *В данной статье говорится о технологиях изобразительного искусства и их развитии в период независимости, создавшихся условиях.*

Ключевые слова: *технологии изобразительного искусства, «Арт-графика», «Искусствоведение», копирование.*

As it is known, due to the achievement of independence, the scientific research carried out in the development of visual art technologies, in color technology

Much space is given to necessary problems such as ancient work and how it got from nature. The rapid development of painting and the direction of painting depends on the modern knowledge and experience of emerging specialists. In this regard, it is necessary to train specialists of bachelor's degree in applied art of art and engineering graphics, who meet the requirements of the time, and are capable in all aspects, in the faculties of "Art-graphics" and "Art studies" of higher educational institutions. The future teacher of fine arts should have a wide knowledge of his profession, as well as the ability to deeply observe the issues of other types of painting, graphics, pencil drawing, applied art. Any science studies the laws of existence that surround us and enriches the knowledge of nature with its research.

In the faculties of "Art and Graphics", "Art Studies" of higher educational institutions, painting, visual art technologies and other specialized subjects are taught from the specialty subjects, and the student acquires such knowledge that he can independently solve problems related to the methods and technology of working with colors. can solve Fine art technology and copying science is focused on refining the practical skills of future fine art teachers, strengthening the skills of working freely with various fine art materials. It also forms such skills as the composition of various fine art objects, the technology of their preparation, the ability to correctly

choose the appropriate material for copying each image, and the determination of painting technology.

The main goals and tasks of fine art technology and copying science are as follows: to provide theoretical knowledge of watercolor, gouache, watercolors from nature, graphics, pencil types and their extraction technologies from nature, the main goal of this manual is to teach the ancient artist. In order to strengthen the students' theoretical knowledge based on scientific sources, information about the technologies of making colors from nature of our masters, painting technology, features of painting works of ancient masters, restoration of miniature technologies, copying is given.

The emergence of easel painting Appolodorus, who worked in the 5th century (BC) admitted that, in the words of Pliny, "The great masters of light and shadow and optical illusion came knocking on my painting door." Ancient authors say that Appolodorus was called a skiagraph (depictor of shadows). That is, it is not surprising that these are the first steps of easel painting, but it is considered the founder of the light-shadow representation of the subject image. Also, the portraits found in Egypt date back to the early centuries of our era. It testifies to how advanced encaustic painting has been in these centuries. The further development of painting in Europe is connected with Christianity. The hardening of Christian mythology led to the decline of Byzantine art in terms of technical methods. During the Renaissance, in Italy and northern European countries, primarily in the Netherlands, a new understanding of icons as paintings emerged. In which complex human relations, the richness of man's relationship with the world, and his inextricable connection with the surrounding environment and nature began to be appreciated. Publications of the first treatises on painting date back to the 7th century.

In London in the middle of the 19th century, European treatises originally created in English in the early 12th-18th centuries were translated into English in parallel. It is interesting that historians, doctors, architects and just painting enthusiasts were interested in the history of painting technology, but those who were not always familiar with the painting technique only organized the information (reconstruction) obtained by the thoughts of contemporaries, for example: Roman the architect Vitruvius openly says that the masters taught no one, not even their relatives or descendants. In the Middle Ages, recipes were collected and the following points were made about it. "Nachinayuhim novo'e sochineniye" - a new protocol for beginners. "It is good that the one who creates something new will not give it to anyone except his son, that is, he will have done a high and just thing by himself, and he will consider all secrets as guaranteed to be kept safely."

REFERENCES

1. Amanullayev. A. Xomaki tasvirlar. Nam. 1992 yil.
2. Alliyarov M. Importance of Excavation Work in the Organization and Enrichment of Museums //Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 35-40.
3. Alliyarov M. THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE GOTHIC PERIOD IS ALSO HISTORICAL //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 182-184.
4. Alliyarov M. Architecture and The Art of Designing //American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 161-165.
5. Alliyarov M. A., Rakhimbaev O. D. MONUMENTAL ARCHITECTURE OF ANCIENT KHOREZM //Матрица научного познания. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 145-152.
6. Alliyarov M., Amaniyazova M. CLASSICAL ARCHITECTURE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 29-31.
7. Alliyarov M. ARCHITECTURE OF THE ROMAN PERIOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 947-952.
8. Alliyarov M. REŃLI SÚWRET BOYINSHA BOLAJAQ SÚWRETLEW ÓNERI OQITIWSHILARINIŃ KOGNITIV ISKERLIGIN RAWAJLANDIRIW //NRJ. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 28-33.
9. Lolaxon B., Ayjamal B. PEDAGOGIK INSTITUTLARDA BILIM BERISH MAZNUNI VA BILIM OLIISH MALAKASINI SHAKILLANTIRISH //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 20. – №. 4. – С. 142-143.
10. Lolaxon B., Ayjamal B. PEDAGOGIK INSTETUTLARDA BILIM BERISH MAZNUNI VA BILIM OLIISH MALAKASINI SHAKILLANTIRISH. – 2023.
11. Бектурсинова Л. ФАСИЛИТАЦИЯ ВОСИТАСИДА ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ //ВЕСТНИК КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА ИМЕНИ БЕРДАХА. – 2017. – Т. 35. – №. 4. – С. 50-53.
12. Bektursinova L. X., Ismailova G. ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FAMILY IN AGGRESSIVE SITUATIONS IN ADOLESCENTS //NRJ. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 949-952.